

THE WEB AS AN EDUCATIONAL TOOL: INTEGRATION OF DIGITAL RESOURCES INTO REMOTE EDUCATION PRACTICES

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ABSTRACT

The development of technology and communication networks caused significant transformations in society and led to the emergence of communication and educational models and processes, new paradigms in terms of Education. With these changes, there was a transposition of educational resources to the virtual arena, and such deanalization has had a direct impact on teachers and students. In addition, the implementation of these systems requires a change in models and conceptions, forcing teachers to assume new roles and interact in ways they are not used to. Given this scenario, the aim of this article is to address the integration of digital resources in remote actions through qualitative bibliographical research. In order to achieve this purpose, we will analyze an experience report of a school manager in the municipal network of Campina Grande, State of Paraíba, who investigated the use of digital resources in remote educational practices in her teaching institution. We intend, in this way, to discuss the obstacles that Education professionals have when dealing with digital resources, to explore questions related to the urgency of incorporating technologies into educators' daily lives, seeking to encourage reflections on the necessary transformations in the educational field, especially in what concerns regarding the use of Information and Communication Technologies.

Keywords: Education. Digital resources. Remote education.

INTRODUCTION

Discussions about the use of digital resources in teaching are not new, as we know. However, with the spread of Information and Communication Technologies and the expansion

of the internet around the world, the issue takes on another aspect, since TDICs have generated countless research on their functionalities and applications in the field of Education.

At the same time, Enhanced by the emergence of *Web 2.0*, the internet ceases to be a simple promoter of access to information and becomes a space in which users read, create, modify and interact with *online content* . From that moment on, in fact, it can be considered a highly valuable alternative for the development of educational practices. In our times, although there is strong resistance to the use of virtual spaces and technologies in education, there is a consensus that we can no longer ignore their applications in the teaching and learning process, as they are already part of the sociocultural reality of the majority of children and young people.

In Pierre Lèvy's understanding, with regard to prognoses regarding the growth in importance of the digital world, it is certain that cyberspace “tends to become the main infrastructure for economic production, transaction and management” (LÈVY,1999, p. 167). This prediction made in the early days of the Internet proved to be correct, as the massive presence of technology in our society also created its own topography, with virtual spaces where it is possible to work with digital resources.

In this sense, focusing on the need to form a student responsible for their own learning, a student prepared to deal with information technologies that are increasingly present in their lives, we perceive digital resources as an indispensable element for learning today. And with regard to the teacher, the fact is that he “has a diverse range of methodological options and possibilities to mediate the knowledge of his students through the insertion of technologies in their pedagogical practices” (SANTOS & TEIXEIRA, 2019, p. 836).

As it is not a simple transition from in-person pedagogical activities to the virtual space, thus requiring the adaptation of strategies, methodologies and pedagogical resources, remote practices and the digital resources that orbit these practices become a viable alternative for dealing with students, thus reducing pedagogical and psychological gaps that can harm learning. With this in mind, our work will analyze so-called remote teaching, which helps to build active learning trajectories, which can be defined as

a teaching modality that presupposes the geographical distance of teachers and students and was temporarily adopted at different levels of education by educational institutions around the world so that school activities are not interrupted” (BEHAR, 2020, p. 26).

Taking into account the importance that virtual learning has in our digital society, our investigation aims to integrate digital resources into remote pedagogical practices, which has proven to be a viable possibility for geographically separated subjects to interact, thus enabling

a redesign of the learning concept. To achieve the purpose of understanding its functionalities, this work will analyze the main concepts of the topic and in order to achieve good results, we will make use of the educational experiences carried out by an educational institution in the municipal network of Campina Grande, State of Paraíba, which carried out an experiment integrating digital resources into remote educational practices.

It should be noted that here we will essentially use a bibliographic analysis methodology, using varied sources, all of them based on relatively contemporary discoveries in the field of Education.

DIGITAL RESOURCES FOR ONLINE EDUCATION

Educator Paulo Freire, when theorizing about the evolution of technology in the 1990s, highlights how the transformations took place in an astonishingly instantaneous manner. When we re-read this reflection today, in the age of the Internet, we cannot help but be even more amazed at the speed of the social, cultural and political changes taking place.

Change is a natural observation of culture and history. What happens is that there are stages, in cultures, in which changes occur quickly. This is what happens today. Technological revolutions shorten the time between one change and another. (FREIRE, 2000, p. 16).

It is a fact that technology, knowledge, the speed of information, the need to know, the forms of knowledge and social organization guide the establishment of a new global context focused on Education and learning. Education, in this sense, can never fail to keep up with ongoing digital changes and innovations. The biggest challenge, by the way, is to build knowledge in a way that stimulates students' autonomous collaboration and creativity.

Furthermore, the use of digital learning tools requires breaking limits, learning from mistakes, managing one's own learning, assuming responsibilities, in short, having the ability to realize that change is feasible. In this scope, Jeong highlights the importance of digital educational resources:

Learning resources can provide unique opportunities for building rich new knowledge. They represent a collection of culture and scientific knowledge accumulated over the years. They can provide a wealth of authentic, up-to-date information not necessarily available in textbooks. They also provide rich contextual information and diverse perspectives on how to interpret the information. As such, resources can be used to help students anchor their learning, examine their understanding from diverse perspectives, make connections across related concepts, and bridge the gap between theoretical understanding and practical knowledge. (JEONG, 2010, p. 85)

Faced with the inexorable march of technology, it is clear that the old learning model, which prioritizes the collection of information and only trains students to apply and reproduce formulas, has become incapable of meeting the demands of society. It is clear, however, that the technological evolution that has reshaped the social order has not yet produced significant changes in education, as we see *in praxis*, in most schools, teaching and learning relationships that are still centered on the teacher.

The growing number of online educational tools and resources that have been developed are, contrary to everyday reality, enhancing the use of the *web* as support for remote teaching and, given this situation, it is increasingly difficult to choose between the many options that best suit adapt to the needs or objectives of a non-face-to-face educational program. It should be noted here that there is no right choice *per se*, there are only devices that are more suitable for certain purposes.

In this sense, it is necessary to perceive technologies as a mediation resource in the teacher-student relationship and in the teaching-learning process, which demands continuous training from the teacher, as the world is constantly transforming. This integration of technology as a mediation resource in education, in turn, also aligns with the need to promote meaningful learning in line with the demands of the contemporary world. Continuously, by adhering to technology, teachers enable a more dynamic and interactive learning environment, capable of engaging students more effectively.

A CASE STUDY

During the COVID-19 pandemic, given the need for social distancing and compliance with the guidelines recommended by the World Health Organization, several concepts were redefined, including, for example, Education. At this time, debates on the use of Digital Information and Communication Technologies have taken new directions, due to the exceptional circumstances experienced and the need to find educational solutions to serve students remotely. The use of digital resources has become an imperative even for those with little familiarity with dealing with technologies or who do not fully understand how important these resources are for teaching/learning.

Situated in such a context, to illustrate the use of digital resources in remote teaching, we will now discuss an experience developed by Edna Câmara Monteiro in a school located in the State of Paraíba, in the city of Campina Grande, during the pandemic caused by COVID-19. The aforementioned work presents experiences that occurred from March to August 2020,

when the school located in the urban area of the city began to operate remotely. The establishment in focus is home to 340 students, who attend from Early Childhood Education to the 5th Year of Elementary School I, in the morning and afternoon periods. The teaching team, at that time, was made up of 15 teachers, distributed across 12 classes.

As an initial procedure, WhatsApp groups were created for all classes, including parents or guardians. Then, based on teacher monitoring and student feedback, teachers sent the content to be studied and the students' daily activities. A group was also organized on WhatsApp for school teachers to inform and monitor pedagogical activities, share teaching strategies and answer questions about pedagogical activities.

Educators sought to create strategies to make remote teaching more dynamic and engaging, in an attempt to promote meaningful learning even at a distance. In general, it was avoided that many activities turned into simple transposition of textbooks to the *online environment*. making Santos' lesson a practice:

posting only PDF texts, linear slide presentations, video classes and/or decontextualized pyrotechnics is an underuse of networked digital and curricular instructionism. We need to engender a complex web of connections and encourage students to enter the content, collaboratively producing knowledge in synchronous and asynchronous communication interfaces. Only then will we have online education (SANTOS, 2020, p. 2)

Upon receiving institutional emails from SEDUC for each student and teacher, a Google Classroom was also created for each class. Along with the creation of the virtual space for these students, a virtual teaching space was created in which plans, documents and reports were shared. Subsequently, there was a need to personalize distance learning to improve student development. Therefore, it was proposed to start classes through real-time face-to-face meetings and record classes to provide reference to those students who did not have access to the class in real time.

One step further, teachers introduced new tools into their distance classes. To this end, the teaching team offered short training courses using social networks, creating learning tools and monitoring groups or individuals, and using tools such as: podcasts, educational games, infographics, Google Drive, among other resources. It should be noted that there was a strong call for educators to use these tools to promote communication, knowledge and access to information, in order to implement the precepts contained in the BNCC with regard to the acquisition of skills

understand, use and create digital information and communication technologies in a critical, meaningful, reflective and ethical way in different

teaching practices, as a pedagogical resource and as a training tool, to communicate, access and disseminate information, produce knowledge, solve problems and enhance learning (BRASIL, 2018, p. 9).

A strategy that greatly contributed to the development of the work was the involvement of parents and guardians in school activities and school supervision. Parents were included in the activities, which increased their affinity with the school institution. With this, it was observed that remote teaching mediated by technological tools provided possibilities for reunification and mediation between students, parents and teachers. Therefore, even during the mandatory social distancing caused by the syndemic, it was necessary to give new meaning to learning and the relationship between school and family. Soon,

The use of ICTs, when well conducted, can promote interaction between teachers and students, exchange of information and experiences, acting as a “window to the world”, that is, it allows the student to conquer other and new spaces. One of the main characteristics of education, involving ICTs, is to promote access to information, which ends up causing a decentralization of the power to communicate in the classroom, previously centered on the figure of the teacher (BIANCHI & HATJE, 2007, p. 293).

In relation to school administration, a remote work system was implemented, making use of communication technologies for service. Administrative tasks began to be conducted remotely, including the production of documents, registrations and even meetings involving employees, teachers, school council, leadership team and parents. It was decided to hold a monthly general assembly of parents through Google Meet, as well as a monthly meeting per class, also using the same platform. The first meetings have already taken place and resulted in significant participation from parents or guardians.

Some difficulties are important to mention, as they highlight the obstacles faced by the school community during the remote teaching period. The school administration had to find creative solutions to guarantee the participation of all students and ensure that the educational process continued in an inclusive and effective way, even in the face of limitations imposed by the technological conditions of students and teachers.

One of the adversities faced was the limited connectivity of some families. Not all students had stable access to the internet, which hindered their active participation in distance learning, while many families did not have essential equipment, such as computers, cell phones or tablets, which made adequate participation in the virtual teaching methods adopted unfeasible. In response to this situation, the school needed to implement a differentiated service for these students, offering printed activities weekly.

There was also concern regarding participation in classes, since students could apparently be present in a class on the virtual teaching platform, but turn off their cameras, either at the teacher's request or by choice, under the justification of improving the quality of the connection. or for other reasons. In the meantime, it is likely that the student was busy with other activities parallel to those proposed by the teacher. This fact makes it difficult to obtain certainty regarding the real engagement and presence of students in the virtual environment. The absence of visual interaction and the possibility of performing multitasking could compromise the degree of student participation, with negative repercussions on the absorption of the content presented.

Another significant challenge was the situation of teachers, who, in the sudden transition to remote teaching, had difficulties adapting to the new reality. To plan, teach classes and monitor different groups of students, teachers needed to rely on a computer or a good cell phone. However, some of them did not have adequate equipment for this task, which made the teaching process even more challenging. Gradually, teachers sought to adapt to this new reality and overcome these technological difficulties.

Thus, one of the lessons that the analyzed experience brought is that learning to manage technologies became an educational necessity in that situation and beyond. Much more than knowing and transmitting the content to be taught, it is necessary to know how to transmit it using ICTs.

CONCLUSION

In recent decades, the field of education has been beset by significant transformations, and especially in previous years, as a result of the syndemic, with the need to transpose in-person teaching to online teaching, there was an immediate imperative *to* rethink the education. Therefore, many challenges that were already addressed in distance education emerged in the debates about how to teach in such difficult conditions, and in this context, remote teaching appeared to be the appropriate option.

Remote teaching, in fact, is not a synonym for distance learning, and although it may be directly related to the use of digital technologies, it has its particularities. As seen in the research that was visited on these pages, the use of digital resources makes it possible to implement innovations *in practice* . However, this myriad of resources and practices is largely determined by the teacher's ability to apply them.

It should be noted that certain digital resources such as Google Meet, YouTube and Skype are essential tools when it comes to Education through remote teaching, as they allow videoconferences, interactive and playful activities that improve knowledge to be held anywhere and at any time. However, such resources are not sufficient and must be related to the educational context. It is necessary to look at the gaps in *on-site* education and try to fill them in order to build network knowledge, providing immediate adaptation to the needs of students.

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